

EFFECT OF SEFT (SPIRITUAL EMOTIONAL FREEDOM TECHNIQUE) THERAPY ON DECREASING LEVELS OF ANXIETY IN STUDENTS OF CLASS VIII SMP THAT WILL FACE MIDDLE SEMESTER EXAMS IN THE 4TH JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL OF MUHAMMADIYAH SURABAYA

Sosilo Yobel^{1*}

¹ STIKES Bodhi Iswara

***Correspondence:**

Sosilo Yobel

Email: syobel@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background: Students who will face an exam experiencing various psychological conditions that can cause students to become anxious. This anxiety can be due to demands from parents, school, social, even the perceptions of the students themselves related to information that has been received in preparing themselves for the exam. One of the actions that can be taken to reduce student anxiety is the therapy of Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique (SEFT).

Objectives: The purpose of this study was the Effect of SEFT Therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) on the Decrease of Anxiety Level in Class VIII Middle School Students Who Will Face the Middle Semester Examination of the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya.

Methods: The research design was *pre-experimental, one group pretest-posttest design*. The sample in this study was all junior high school students of class VIII-C who would face the Mid Semester Examination at the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya with 30 people taken by the technique *Total Sampling*. Data analysis using the *Wilcoxon Test*, namely SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) to reduce anxiety levels.

Results: Based on the Wilcoxon Test the value of $Z = -4,956$ and the value of $p \text{ Value} = 0,000$ so that ($p < \alpha$) so that H_1 accepted H_0 rejected means that there is influence of SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) to decrease anxiety levels of students in class VIII who will face the exam Semester at the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya.

Conclusion: SEFT therapy can be given to students who will face the test with the approach taken spiritually, discussion and interpersonal communication by knocking 18 key points in the human body is SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*). SEFT therapy can provide calmness to students psychologically.

Key words: SEFT Therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*), anxiety, emotional.

INTRODUCTION

Generally, when approaching the Exam, students experience feelings of nervousness or anxiety, from this feeling arises a feeling of lack of confidence. The fact that feeling nervous and anxious is not only experienced when students will face the Middle Semester

Exams but also other school exams. Devaney (2010) explains that anxiety can influence student achievement. Although the students have learned long ago, and prepare as much as possible for the exam, there is something that affects the students' work on the problems that feelings of anxiety or

nervousness arising from within, then the student fails in doing a variety of school exams.

Dawood (2016) states that anxiety is a general phenomenon that is a cause of poor academic performance in students. Someone experiencing feelings of anxiety, nervousness, or tension in the face of an uncertain situation, means that person is experiencing anxiety. The learning process often makes teenagers experience stress and anxiety because of the many demands and expectations that must be met both from the school and family environment. This anxiety will affect the outcome of achieving targeted students (Tresna, 2011). Academic values obtained from an examination are considered as manifestations of student achievement in the academic field. If students successfully pass the test with good grades, students are considered successful in answering the demands of the school and family in the academic field. Meanwhile, students who get poor results from a test will give birth to problems in students, especially the lack of interest in the world of education (Faried & Nashori, 2012).

Hall, B. & Tyish (2005) state the results of a study conducted by Hill & Sarason regarding children's anxiety measured using the TASC (Test Anxiety Scale Children) that 4-5 million elementary school children and junior high school students have a strong experience of anxiety in the exam. Related to this, Santrock (2007) explains that students have a high level of anxiety because the expectations of parents are unrealistic about the abilities possessed by children. The national prevalence of anxiety disorders is experienced by middle school students in Indonesia as much as 4.7%. Whereas in East Java there is a percentage of 68.3% of junior high school students experiencing anxiety. In

Surabaya itself, the prevalence level of anxiety for junior high school students is 20.2% (Health Department, 2017).

The phenomenon of high anxiety in facing examinations on students, of course, can hinder the learning goals that students want to achieve. Tresna's (2011) study found anxiety facing exams was triggered by uncontrolled states of mind, feelings and motor behavior. Uncontrolled cognitive manifestations cause the mind to become tense, uncontrolled affective manifestations lead to feelings of bad things happening, and uncontrolled motoric behavior causes students to become nervous and trembling when facing an exam. State of anxiety experienced continuous Siwa if allowed then that anxiety resulted in negative behavior of students to the school, such as: rejection of school, low self-esteem, withdrawal, reluctant to appear, and not confident. Faried & Nashori (2012) said that anxiety can be controlled by self-control in a person. Self-control is related to how individuals control their emotions as well as their inner drives. The ability to control themselves allows someone to behave more directed and can channel the impulses in themselves correctly and not deviate from the norms of society. Self-control is focused on strengthening yourself positively, punishing yourself, manipulating emotional conditions, monitoring yourself so you can control anxiety, which consists of concentration, not trusting yourself, often thinking about danger, anxiety, and worry.

Therefore, anxiety is just as important to study in increasing self-confidence, so anxiety needs to be overcome. In terms of overcoming anxiety, students need a problem solving to improve their ability to prepare for the exam and reduce anxiety. One of the methods needed is using the SEFT (*Spiritual*

Emotional Freedom Technique) to help students reduce anxiety levels.

METHODS

Study Design

This study was a *pre-experimental* study with research *one group pretest-posttest design* which revealed a causal relationship by involving one group of subjects. The group of subjects was observed before the intervention was then observed again after intervention. After intervention, researchers compared the results of pre-tests with post-test results (Nursalam, 2016).

Table 1. Drawing Design Research *one-group pretest-posttest design*.

Subject	Pre	Treatment of	Post-Test
KO		I	O1
	Time 1	Time 2	Time 3

Description:

- K : Subject (class VIII middle school student)
- O : Observation of anxiety level before intervention
- I : Intervention (SEFT therapy)
- O1 : Observation of the level of anxiety after intervention

Setting

This study was conducted in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya.

Research Subject

The population in this study were all students VIII-C in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya with number of 30 students. The sample in this study was all students of class VIII-C who would face the Mid Semester Examination at the 4th Junior

High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya, amounting to 30 students.

Instruments

The measuring instrument used was a manual procedure for Spiritual Emotional Freedom Techniques and the observation sheets Numeric Rating Scale (NRS).

Data Analysis

The data has been analyzed using Wilcoxon signed rank test with significance level of 5%.

Ethical Consideration

This research has gone through an ethical test from the STIKES Bodhi Iswara Surabaya and obtained permission from the Head of the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya.

RESULTS

Based on the results of the collection of data from 30 respondents obtained the general data of respondents that included age and gender.

Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Table 2. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Age in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya (n = 30).

Age (Years)	Amount (frequency)	Percentage (%)
12	1	3%
13	10	34%
14	15	50%
15	4	13%
Total	30	100%

Based on table 2 found that half of students as many as 15 respondents (50%)

aged 14 years old and a small age of 12 years old students namely 1 student with a percentage of 3%.

Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

According to the table 3 obtained the sex of class VIII-C students is partly dominated by male students as many as 17 students (57 %) and 13 students almost half were female with a percentage of 43%.

Table 3. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Gender in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya (n = 30).

Gender	Amount (frequency)	Percentage (%)
Male	17	57%
Female	13	43%
Total	30	100%

Cross Tabulation of Anxiety Levels Before and After SEFT Therapy Students of Class VIII-C at the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya

Table 4. Cross Tabulation of Anxiety Levels Before and After SEFT Therapy Students of Class VIII-C at the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya (n = 30).

			Posttest				
			Normal	Light	Medium	Heavy	Total
Pretest	Medium	Frequency	4	5	0	0	9%
		pre-test	44.4%	55.6%	0%	0%	100%%
		post-test	80%	83.3%	0%	0%	30%
		% Of total	13.3%	16.7%	0%	0%	30%
	Heavy	Frequency	0	1	9	0	10%
		pre-test	0%	10%	90%	0%	100%%
		posttest	0%	16.7%	64.3%	0 %	33.3%
		% Total	0%	3.3%	30%	0%	33.3%
	Panic	Frequency	1	0	5	5	11%
		pre-test	9.1%	0%	45.5%	45.5%	100%%
		post-test	20%	0%	35.7%	100%	36.7%
		% total	3.3%	0%	16.7%	16.7%	36.7%
Total	Frequency	5	6	14	5	30	
	% pre test	16.7%	20%	46.7%	16.7%	100%	

Based on table 4 showed that students of class VIII-C as many as 4 students during the pretest experienced moderate levels of anxiety while post-test did not experience anxiety, and 5 people others experience mild anxiety. 1 person at the pretest experienced severe anxiety when the posttest experienced mild anxiety while 9 other students at the time of the posttest experienced moderate

anxiety. 1 student at the time of pre-test post-test experience panic when not experiencing anxiety, 5 students when post-test anxiety and 5 others were currently experiencing severe anxiety post-test so that the total number of 30 students.

DISCUSSION

Levels of Pre-Giving SEFT (Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique) Therapy

Based on table 4, the level of anxiety before administration of SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) obtained almost half (37%) of anxiety at the panic level and the lowest percentage of 30% of students experienced moderate anxiety.

According to Suliswati (2014) panic is a loss of control, it is unable to do anything even with orders. There is an increase in motor activity, reduced ability to relate to others, perceptual aberrations and loss of rational thought, unable to function effectively. Usually accompanied by personality disorganization.

Many factors influence the level of anxiety, namely age. Anxiety disorders begin in the early teens, between the ages of 14 and 25 years, but the numbers continue to increase after the age of 35 (Puri, Laking, & Treasaden, 2011). Another factor that affects anxiety is suppressed emotions where anxiety can occur if an individual is unable to find a way out for his own feelings in this personal relationship, especially if he suppresses anger or frustration for a very long time. In line with the theory, according to Vienna (2010) states that students have bad thoughts when going to take an exam, this affects student performance while doing the exam. The mind is based on negative thoughts that cause anxiety or anxiety in students. Other opinions reveal that students experience anxiety or fear when facing an exam, it can be seen from physical, psychological, social symptoms. If students experience anxiety when they want to take an exam, he will experience a

decreased performance, so students become less optimal in doing the exam. Anxiety in addition to being influenced by internal factors is also influenced by external factors such as family support, and the environment. So, from that the importance of cooperation between teachers, families, and researchers to support each other in order to improve the quality of life of students.

Level of Anxiety After Giving SEFT (Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique) Therapy

Based on table 4 showed that the level of anxiety after therapy in class VIII-C with a total of 30 students almost half with a percentage of 46% had moderate anxiety and a small percentage of students with a percentage of 17% did not experience anxiety and experience severe anxiety, on anxiety before and after administration of therapy p value = 0,000, which means that there is a significant difference between the level of anxiety before administration of therapy with after therapy. According to Suliswati (2014) mild anxiety is divided into two categories, which are mild and mild for a long time. This anxiety is very beneficial for the development of one's personality, because this anxiety can be a challenge for an individual to overcome it. Mild anxiety that appears briefly is a reasonable anxiety that occurs to individuals due to threatening situations and the individual cannot overcome it, resulting in anxiety. This anxiety will be beneficial for individuals to be more careful in facing the same situations in the future. Old mild anxiety is anxiety that can be overcome but because the individual does not immediately

address the cause of anxiety, then the anxiety will settle for a long time in the individual. While moderate anxiety is an individual focusing only on the mind that is of concern to him, there is a narrowing of the perception field, can still do something with the direction of others.

One of the factors that influence anxiety is influenced by gender. The number who suffer from both acute and chronic anxiety reaches 5% of the population, with a ratio between women and men 2 to 1 (Hawari, 2014). Women are more at risk of experiencing stress in response to psychological disorders, but male coping mechanisms are higher in dealing with problems (Yeh, Wen, & Chang, 2008). Gender / gender is closely related to disease response, anxiety, and coping use in dealing with health problems (Ratnawati, 2011). In line with the theory above, the results of data analysis are many male students who are more prone to experience levels of anxiety than severe levels, panic becomes mild and normal.

In addition to this the *Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique* (SEFT) developed from *Emotional Freedom Technique* (EFT), combines spiritual elements in the stages of their implementation. The goal is to see human potential as a whole, thoroughly and explore the deepest human potential, one of which is *Spiritual*. In the *Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique* (SEFT), the spiritual element refers to the transpersonal psychological approach. Transpersonal in its technique has a goal to *re-connect an individual* with the source of wisdom that is in it, combining between *conscious ego* and *subconscious* that is inside with the aim of activating and developing an individual's ability to heal himself. The definition is also supported by

transpersonal views expressed by Vaughan, saying that one of the assumptions underlying transpersonal psychotherapy is that every human being has a movement for spiritual growth, the capacity to learn and grow throughout life, and this process can be facilitated by psychotherapy. In line with the above opinion, Rowan stated that psychotherapy is about someone's courage to open what is inside him. Spiritual methods are also a way of venturing to open what is inside. Therefore, psychotherapy means it is also a spiritual practice (Praise & Vigor, 2015).

Based on the above description *Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique* (SEFT) which also consists of three phases including *the sett-up*, aims to ensure that the body's energy flows are directed appropriately. The step is to neutralize psychological resistance which is usually in the form of spontaneous negative thoughts or negative unconscious beliefs. If it is understood in religious terms, *the set-up* is a submission prayer to God Almighty, *the settlements* consist of 2 activities which are the first to say the surrender sentence which can be in the form of prayer and receive for what happens to him with great sincerity and sincere (Zainuddin, 2012). The same surrender attitude or sentence is thought to give an optimistic attitude to someone so that positive feelings arise such as feeling happy, feeling happy, satisfied, successful, feeling loved, or feeling safe

SEFT (Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique) Therapy for Decreasing Anxiety Levels

The level of student anxiety will be different from one another because it is influenced by how to deal with each individual's different problems. One method

that can reduce anxiety, is to use SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) so that it results in anxiety and decreased anxiety. This can be proven by decreasing the number of anxieties according to table 5.6 which obtained p Value = 0,000, meaning that there are differences in anxiety levels before and after intervention. Anxiety is a normal concomitant of the growth of new experiences, and the discovery of one's own identity and the search for meaning in life. Conversely, pathological anxiety is a response that is not appropriate to the stimulus given based on the intensity or duration. Anxiety includes several biological systems, especially in the brain. Some of these systems include: (1) autonomic systems of *neurotransmitters* which include norepinephrine, serotonin, GABA (*Gamma Aminobutyric Acid*), and *aplasia*, (3) brain imaging studies, (4) genetic researchers, (5) neuroanatomic considerations which include the limbic system and cerebral context (Kaplan, Sadock, & Grebb, 2010).

The use of *Emotional Freedom Technique* (EFT) for acupressure points strengthens cognitive and components *exposure* serves to show a reduction in fear after stimulation *acupoint*. In Church (2012) study states that acupuncture that uses functional magnetic resonance imaging to measure its impact on the brain, acupuncture was found to directly modulate the stress response by decreasing the regulation of *hyperarousal* amygdala and other structures from the limbic system. In line with this statement Cherkin, also explained that the pressure at the acupuncture point had been found to be as efficacious as needling acupuncture.

In the clinical realm EFT itself has been used as a valid method in many studies in the field of study. In his research, one of the

figures who helped develop *Emotional Freedom Technique* (EFT) stated that the therapy fulfilled the standard criteria of APA (*American Psychological Association*), where EFT has been used in several studies and practices widely including summarizing studies on (1) psychological conditions such as anxiety, depression, phobias, and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), (2) physiological problems such as illness and autoimmune conditions, (3) professional and sports performance, and (4) physiological mechanisms of EFT Clinical measures and several other experiments. Three important ingredients of the clinical *Emotional Freedom Technique* (EFT) are explained: *exposure*, *cognitive shift*, and acupressure. This is evidence of an important element in EFT's success (Church et al., 2012).

According to Bakara, Ibrahim, & Sriati (2012) this spiritual belief will provide a sense of calm and positive hope for those who experience pain, so that it is expected to reduce anxiety. Spiritual therapy gives rise to relaxation and health responses, can lead to confidence in self-care, and is beneficial to anxiety and panic in terminal patients that can lead to calmness.

Calm or in psychology is called relaxed by Maimunah & Retnowati (2011) stating is a method used to help humans learn to reduce or control physiological reactivity which causes problems for themselves besides relax is used to reduce individual physiological turmoil and bring individuals into a state calmer both physically and psychologically. One study has proven that the relaxation intervention approach given to pregnant women has not found a significant result that is able to reduce anxiety.

Based on the above description *Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique* (SEFT) which also consists of three phases including

the sett-up, aims to ensure that the body's energy flows are directed appropriately. The step is to neutralize psychological resistance which is usually in the form of spontaneous negative thoughts or negative unconscious beliefs. If it is understood in religious terms, *the set-up* is a submission prayer to God Almighty, *the settlements* consist of 2 activities which are the first to say the surrender sentence which can be in the form of prayer and receive for what happens to him with great sincerity and sincere (Zainuddin, 2012).

Attitude or a similar sentence is alleged resignation will give an upbeat attitude in a person that appears positive feelings like happiness, joy, satisfaction, success, feel loved, or felt safe. Emotional attitude with God. So, in similar conditions, humans are in a calm and normal state, in the balance of chemical compounds and body hormones. In other words, the condition of its nature, in accordance with the nature of its occurrence, is physically and mentally healthy (Zainuddin, 2012).

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been done on the effect of therapy SEFT (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) to decrease the anxiety level of junior high school students of class VIII which will face Middle Semester Exam in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya can be concluded that:

1. The level of anxiety of students of class VIII-C in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya before being given SEFT therapy (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) almost half experienced panic.
2. Anxiety level class VIII-C in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah

Surabaya after therapy is given SEFT (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) almost half experiencing moderate anxiety and mild.

There SEFT (*Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique*) therapeutic effect to decrease the level of anxiety in the eighth-grade junior high school students who will face Middle Semester Exam in the 4th Junior High School of Muhammadiyah Surabaya.

SUGGESTION

To reduce the anxiety level of students in facing the exam, the school can work together with health workers who master SEFT (*Spiritual Emotional Technique*) Therapy to do the SEFT Therapy.

REFERENCES

- Bakara, DM, Ibrahim, K., & Sriati, A. (2012). Influence of Spiritual Emotional Freedom Techniques (SEFT) on the Levels of Symptoms of Depression, Anxiety, and Stress.
- Church, D., Yount, & Brooks. (2012). Single-Session Reduction of the Intensity of Traumatic Memories in Abused Adolescents After EFT A Randomized Controlled Pilot Study. *Traumatology*, 18(3), 73–79.
- Dawood. (2016). Learning by Collaboration: The Impact of Cooperative Learning on Students Essay Writing Skills at Graduation Level in Pakistan.
- Ministry of Health. (2017). *Health Research and Development Agency of the Indonesian Ministry of Health*.
- Devaney, AT (2010). Anxiety on Attitude Graduate Students in Campus vs. Online Statistics Courses. *Journal Statistics of Education*, 18(1).
- Fariad & Nashori. (2012). *The development*

- of psychology is an approach throughout the life span. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Hall, B., & Tyish, S. (2005). *Is Test Anxiety a Form of Specific Social Phobia?* University of Maryland College.
- Hawari, D. (2014). *Stress, anxiety and depression management*. Jakarta: FKUI.
- Kaplan, HI, Sadock, BJ, & Grebb, JA (2010). *Psychopsy Synopsis of Clinical Psychiatric Behavior*. Tangerang: Binarupa Aksara.
- Maimunah, A., & Retnowati, S. (2011). Effect of Relaxation Training with Dhikr to Overcome Anxiety in First Pregnant Women. *Islamic Psychology Journal*, 8(1), 1–22.
- Nursalam. (2016). *Research Methodology in Nursing: Practical Approach* (4th ed.). Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
- Puji, PP, & Vigor, WH (2015). Transpersonal Therapy. UGM Faculty of Psychology. *Psychology Bulletin*, 23(2).
- Puri, BK, Laking, PJ, & Treasaden, IH (2011). *Psychiatric Textbook* (2nd ed.). Jakarta: EGC.
- Ratnawati, L. (2011). Relationship between Family Support and Depression Levels in Patients Failure Ginja undergoing Hemodialysis Therapy in RSUD dr. Abdoer Rahem Situbondo. *Journal of Health and Sport*, 3, 285–362.
- Santrock, JW (2007). *Adolesance: Development of adolescence*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Suliswati. (2014). *Basic Mental Health Nursing* (3rd ed.). Jakarta: EGC.
- Tresna, IG (2011). Effectiveness of behavioral counseling with systematic desentization techniques to reduce anxiety against testing, 1, 90-104.
- Vienna, S. (2010). *Learning Strategies Oriented to Educational Process Standards*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia group.
- Yeh, PP, Wen, T., & Chang, C. (2008). Costs of Metabolic Syndrome-related Diseases Induced by Obesity in Taiwan. *Obes Rev*, 9(1), 68–73.
- Zainuddin, AF (2012). *Spiritual Emotional Freedom Technique (SEFT)*. Jakarta: Afzan Publishing.